
LIBRARIAN CATCHES THIEF: SURFACING SUPPLY CHAIN ATTACK CAMPAIGNS VIA DOCUMENT SIMILARITY IN AN AI AGENT SKILL REGISTRY

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© Gale Fagan

Edgewood University
gfagan@edgewood.edu

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ABSTRACT

AI agent skill marketplaces distribute natural-language instruction files following the Agent Skills standard, an open format adopted by over 30 platforms. Unlike code registries such as npm and PyPI, no marketplace examined in this study performs documented deduplication or similarity checking at ingest. In early 2026, the ClawHub registry for the OpenClaw agent framework experienced a supply chain attack campaign in which threat actors uploaded hundreds of near-identical skills that directed users to install credential-stealing malware.

A MinHash locality-sensitive hashing pipeline processed 31,634 skill files from the ClawHub registry and 31 community repositories with no security-specific tuning. At a 90% Jaccard threshold, 7,147 files fell into 2,622 similarity clusters, and all 337 known malicious skills present in the corpus appeared in a cluster. Among the 38 clusters containing at least 10 files, 30 held confirmed malicious content (78.9%, 95% CI [63.7, 88.9]), and every cluster with more than 20 files was malicious (95% CI [74.1, 100]).

Document similarity clustering has proven effective in code registries; these results show the technique transfers to text-based ecosystems where campaigns reuse templates at scale. Git commit history suggests that the largest campaign had already formed a detectable cluster in the archive by the time of public disclosure, under conservative assumptions about disclosure timing. These results support the use of document similarity as a lightweight, signature-free first pass for publish-time security screening in text-based registries.

Keywords Supply chain security · AI agent ecosystems · Document similarity · Locality-sensitive hashing · Malware detection · Software supply chain attacks

1 Introduction

Software supply chain attacks exploit the trust relationship between package registries and their consumers. A growing body of work documents these attacks across npm [24, 2, 5], PyPI [3, 4], and other code distribution ecosystems [23]. Detection methods range from behavioral analysis of package scripts to structural clustering of code artifacts. Clustering approaches have shown particular effectiveness for identifying coordinated campaigns that reuse templates at scale [2, 3].

A new category of software distribution ecosystem now exists alongside these code registries. AI agent skill marketplaces distribute capabilities as markdown instruction files following the Agent Skills standard [1], an open specification adopted by over 30 platforms including Claude Code, GitHub Copilot, Cursor, OpenAI Codex, and Gemini CLI. These SKILL.md files contain YAML frontmatter and natural-language instructions that direct an AI agent's behav-

ior. Installation is simply a file copy. The ecosystem lacks package manager verification, linking mechanisms, and deduplication.

ClawHub hosted 2,857 skills when Koi Security published their initial analysis on February 1, 2026. This number grew to over 10,700 by February 16 and to 23,806 by our March 13 archive. This rapid growth invited supply chain attackers. Koi Security’s ClawHavoc report [8] documented 341 malicious skills (later expanded to 824) that used fake prerequisite instructions embedded in skill documentation to deliver the AMOS information stealer. Antiy CERT [11] independently analyzed the same campaign, identifying 1,184 malicious skills across historical repository data. Koi’s detection relied on behavioral pattern matching during a complete audit of all published skills.

Six independent groups have analyzed this ecosystem retrospectively (Section 7), primarily through behavioral and binary analysis. None proposed a preventive, publish-time mechanism, even though code registries with comparable threat models already use structural defenses [2, 3]. No published work has examined whether these methods, validated on AST representations of JavaScript and Python packages, transfer to ecosystems distributing natural-language artifacts, where no abstract syntax tree exists and detection must rely on document-level features. We investigate three research questions:

RQ1 What does MinHash document similarity reveal about the duplication landscape of an AI skill marketplace?

RQ2 Does the method detect known supply chain campaigns, and at what cluster size thresholds does it achieve actionable precision?

RQ3 How does structural detection compare to behavioral detection in coverage and blind spots?

We applied MinHash locality-sensitive hashing [13] with 3-word shingles, implemented in Plugin Librarian, an open-source duplicate detection tool originally built to identify redundant skills that waste agent context windows. The tool’s design predates and is independent of the ClawHavoc disclosure; its application to the full March 2026 archive was a deliberate retrospective evaluation. The resulting similarity clusters contained all files from the largest coordinated supply chain campaign documented in this ecosystem. Validation against IOC lists from Koi Security [8] and Antiy CERT [11] confirmed the clustering method captures these campaigns: all 337 Koi-documented malicious skills present in the archive appeared within clusters, and we recovered 9 of 12 Antiy-documented attacker accounts (8 via cluster membership, 1 via payload inspection within clustered files).

To our knowledge, this is the first structural analysis of an AI skill marketplace (31,634 files across 32 repositories). The results demonstrate that the detection principles established by ACME [2] and MPHunter [3] transfer to this artifact type: document similarity clustering detects coordinated campaigns despite operating on natural language rather than code. Precision and recall are evaluated against ground truth from six independent security analyses. The scanning tool and dataset are released as open source for reproducibility.

2 Background

2.1 AI Skill Marketplaces

The Agent Skills specification [1] provides an open standard for defining AI agent capabilities via text files. Anthropic originally developed the specification, which over 30 agent platforms have since adopted, including GitHub Copilot, Cursor, OpenAI Codex, and Gemini CLI [1]. Capabilities reside in SKILL.md files containing YAML frontmatter alongside natural language instructions. Users install skills by copying the file into a local directory, meaning the ecosystem lacks integrity checks, signature verification, and deduplication.

OpenClaw was an early adopter of this format. Its primary registry, ClawHub, operates as a GitHub repository (openclaw/skills) that aggregates published skills, while independent community marketplaces curate subsets or publish original content. Certain aggregators re-publish skills without tracking modifications or providing attribution. While the attacks documented here targeted OpenClaw, format standardization means these attack patterns and detection methods apply to any platform implementing the Agent Skills specification.

This ecosystem differs from registries like npm or PyPI in a way that alters the landscape for both attack and detection. Skills are natural language instructions interpreted by an AI agent, not executable code. A malicious skill delivers its payload by instructing the agent to download and execute a binary, or by deceiving a human user into installing a fake prerequisite. The instruction set itself forms the attack surface.

2.2 Threat Model for Text-Based Package Ecosystems

AI skill marketplaces present a threat model distinct from code registries. We identified three attack vectors specific to this ecosystem.

Fake prerequisite injection. A malicious skill directs the user or agent to download a binary from an attacker-controlled URL under the guise of a required dependency. On macOS, users are instructed to paste obfuscated shell commands from clipboard-sharing services (glot.io, reentry.co) into Terminal. On Windows, the payload is a password-protected ZIP archive hosted on GitHub, where the password protection bypasses automated antivirus scanning. The ClawHavoc campaign delivered AMOS (Atomic macOS Stealer), a commodity malware-as-a-service product available for \$500–1,000/month that targets browser credentials, cryptocurrency wallets, and SSH keys [8, 12]. Attackers often copy legitimate skills and inject a small block of prerequisite instructions.

Agent-directed execution. Because AI agents interpret these skills, an attacker can embed instructions causing the agent to execute shell commands, fetch remote resources, or alter system configurations [21, 26]. The agent’s instruction parser becomes the target for social engineering.

Persistence through configuration poisoning. OpenClaw agents maintain state in `SOUL.md` and `MEMORY.md` files. A malicious skill can instruct the agent to modify these state files, establishing persistence across sessions in the manner of indirect prompt injection [21]. This persistence mechanism is specific to AI ecosystems and has no analogue in traditional package registries.

The copy-based installation model compounds these vectors. The absence of provenance tracking and checksumming makes it impossible to distinguish a first-party skill from a modified copy containing injected payloads.

2.3 Clustering-Based Detection in Package Registries

Ohm et al. [18, 2] first established that supply chain campaigns rely on reusable code templates, making them detectable via structural clustering. They applied Markov Chain Clustering (MCL) to abstract syntax tree (AST) representations of npm packages, achieving $F1 = 0.99$ on known malware families and automatically generating detection signatures from cluster centroids. MPHunter [3] extended clustering to PyPI `setup.py` scripts, using outlier detection within clusters to discover 60 previously unknown malicious packages. EMPHunter [4] generalized MPHunter’s method across npm and PyPI, demonstrating cross-ecosystem applicability.

These methods share a structural assumption: attack campaigns produce many similar artifacts. The operational pattern of mass template reuse leaves a detectable structural fingerprint, regardless of whether the artifact is a JavaScript module, a Python setup script, or a markdown instruction file. Clustering finds that fingerprint without requiring prior knowledge of the payload or attack technique.

MinHash and LSH originate in web-scale near-duplicate detection [13, 14]. Unlike SimHash [16], which estimates angular distance on fixed-length vectors, MinHash estimates set-based Jaccard similarity directly on variable-length shingle sets. Applying it to skill files serves the same deduplication principle as web-page detection, applied in a security context where duplicates signal coordinated attacks.

The gap in this literature is the artifact type. All published clustering-based *security* detection operates on code-level representations (ASTs, source files, setup scripts). No published work applies these methods to natural-language documents, despite the emergence of ecosystems where skills, prompts, and agent configurations are the distributed artifacts. Section 7 surveys complementary detection methods and the prior analyses providing ground truth for our evaluation.

3 Methodology

3.1 Analysis Timeline

Plugin Librarian was developed between January 2 and January 18, 2026 to solve a practical problem: skills lie buried within plugin directory trees lacking standard discovery mechanisms, and duplicate content across marketplace repositories inflates agent context windows. The tool indexes and compares skills prior to installation, helping users locate available skills and avoid redundant ones. The tool lacked security analysis functionality and was not designed for attack detection, a fact verifiable from its commit history and documentation.

The original similarity scan occurred on January 2, 2026, covering 7,183 files from community marketplace repositories only. The ClawHub archive was excluded from this initial scan. Koi Security published the ClawHavoc threat

report on February 1, 2026, one month after the tool’s development, followed by an expanded update on February 16, 2026.

We cloned the ClawHub archive on March 13, 2026 from the `openclaw/skills` GitHub repository and scanned it the same day (31,634 files including community repositories). Cluster inspection and IOC cross-referencing took place on March 14, 2026.

We were aware of the ClawHavoc report prior to scanning the ClawHub archive. We did not modify the scanner for security analysis; it ran with the same MinHash/LSH parameters used in the January duplicate-detection scan. While prior knowledge of ClawHavoc informed cluster interpretation, the IOC cross-reference validates that the clustering method independently captures known campaigns. All accounts checked against the Antiy CERT author list were already documented.

The archive represents a point-in-time snapshot. Skills removed from ClawHub before March 13, 2026 do not appear in the corpus.

Temporal analysis. We extracted commit timestamps from the unshallowed ClawHub mirror (70,091 commits) using `git log` with per-file first-commit dates. These timestamps reflect when the mirror recorded each file, not the original publication time on the upstream registry; mirror lag means original publication was earlier. Git timestamps are author-controllable, so temporal figures reported in Section 8 are upper bounds. Because no primary source exposes a precise publication time for Koi Security’s initial ClawHavoc report, all temporal offsets are anchored on a conservative assumption that public disclosure occurred at 2026-02-01T00:00:00Z.

3.2 Dataset Construction

The corpus comprises two sources:

ClawHub registry. The `openclaw/skills` GitHub repository contained 23,806 `SKILL.md` files as of the archive date (23,654 after applying the 100-character minimum filter). This repository aggregates all skills published to the ClawHub marketplace.

Community marketplaces. We included 31 additional GitHub repositories that independently curate or publish OpenClaw skills. Table 1 lists all included repositories alongside their file counts.

Table 1: Repositories included in the corpus. File counts reflect `SKILL.md` files meeting the 100-character minimum after filtering.

Repository	Files
clawhub-archive	23,654
claude-code-plugins-plus	2,396
antigravity-awesome-skills	1,249
sundial-awesome-openclaw-skills	933
claude-code-templates	715
curated	639
han	429
alirezarezvani-claude-skills	421
leoyei-openclaw-master-skills	361
claude-scientific-skills	175
claude-code-workflows	146
mag-claude-plugins	131
<i>20 repositories with <50 files each</i>	385
Total (32 repositories)	31,634

Inclusion criteria required files named `SKILL.md` with a minimum of 100 characters of content. This 100-character floor excludes stub files and empty placeholders, yielding a final filtered corpus of 31,634 files.

Selection of community repositories. We identified the 31 community repositories via GitHub code search for files named `SKILL.md` containing OpenClaw-compatible YAML frontmatter (query: `filename:SKILL.md "description:"`, executed January 2, 2026). This search returned 48 repositories; we excluded 17 as forks, empty, or containing non-skill content. We included all remaining publicly accessible repositories at the time of collection. No repositories were selected or excluded based on known malicious content.

3.3 Similarity Analysis

We used MinHash with locality-sensitive hashing (LSH) [13, 15] as implemented in the `datasketch` library [17] (version 1.6.0+) for Python.

Tokenization. We normalized each file’s content to lowercase and collapsed whitespace. Punctuation other than hyphens was removed (regex: `[\^a-z0-9\s\-_]`). This normalization partially destroys embedded URLs and YAML key names; we accept this trade-off because the clustering target is template structure and payload content is analyzed separately (Section 3.5). The normalized text was split into word-level 3-grams (shingles). For documents shorter than three words, individual words were used as shingles. For documents under three characters, the text itself served as a single shingle.

MinHash computation. We converted each shingle set into a MinHash signature using 128 hash permutations. We used the `datasketch` library default and did not tune this value for this analysis. At this configuration, the standard error for Jaccard similarity estimation is approximately $\pm 1/\sqrt{128} \approx 8.8\%$, sufficient for distinguishing high-similarity clusters (90%+) from moderate overlap but coarser than the 256- or 512-permutation configurations typical in web-scale deduplication [14]. Running the full analysis with five distinct random seeds (1, 42, 123, 456, 789) produced cluster counts ranging from 2,558 to 2,622 (a 2.4% spread). The primary analysis used the library’s default seed, which generated the maximum count and thus provided the most conservative precision denominator. Pairwise Adjusted Rand Index scores remained ≥ 0.9999 across all ten pairs, confirming that the clustering is robust to hash function randomness.

LSH indexing. MinHash signatures were indexed in a MinHashLSH structure with a configurable similarity threshold. We applied a 90% threshold for the primary analysis reported in this paper. Results at 70% (the tool’s default) appear in Table 2 to illustrate threshold sensitivity.

Cluster formation. Files were processed sequentially in index order. For each unassigned file, the LSH structure returned all candidate matches exceeding the similarity threshold. The query file and its candidates formed a single cluster; all members were marked as assigned and skipped in subsequent iterations (minimum cluster size: 2 files). Because of this greedy first-match strategy, cluster membership depends on processing order: a file assigned to an early cluster cannot appear in a later one, even given a valid match. Given a fixed file ordering, the process is deterministic. We did not perform a file-order permutation experiment; the seed robustness analysis (five seeds, $\text{ARI} \geq 0.9999$) measures hash function stability but does not isolate the effect of input ordering. Within each cluster, all pairwise Jaccard similarities were computed from the MinHash signatures to populate a similarity matrix.

Cluster classification. We classified clusters into three mutually exclusive types:

A *scaffold* cluster contains 5 or more files from a single marketplace with mean pairwise similarity $\geq 98\%$, representing near-duplicate template files originating from one source. An *internal* cluster also contains files from only one marketplace but does not meet the scaffold thresholds (5+ files, 98%+ similarity). A *cross-marketplace* cluster spans two or more marketplaces.

Threshold selection rationale. We performed a threshold sweep at 70%, 75%, 80%, 85%, 90%, and 95% on `SKILL.md` files to assess detection sensitivity (Table 2). Recall against the Koi IOC list held constant at 99.2% across all six thresholds, confirming that malicious campaigns cluster well above the 70% floor. Precision at the ≥ 20 cluster size threshold reached 100% only at 90% and above, establishing 90% as the lowest threshold that eliminates false positives for large-cluster triage. The reported confidence interval at 90% is not corrected for the search over six thresholds. We selected 90% for the primary analysis on this basis.

Why MinHash. The duplicate detection tool already implemented MinHash (Section 3.6); the security application emerged from inspecting its output. We compare against baselines (Section 5.2) to verify MinHash provides value beyond simpler methods. MinHash requires no training data, scales linearly in corpus size for signature computation, and supports tunable similarity thresholds through LSH.

3.4 Ground Truth and Validation

Koi Security published the ClawHavoc threat report on February 1, 2026, documenting 341 malicious ClawHub skills attributed to a coordinated AMOS stealer campaign. An expanded update on February 16, 2026 increased the count to 824. Antiy CERT independently identified 1,184 malicious skills across historical repository data [11]. The individual skill slugs (package names) reside in Koi’s Clawdex database (`clawdex.koi.security`), accessible through a per-skill API that returns a verdict (benign, malicious, or unknown) with supporting evidence.

We treated the 341 original IOC slugs from the Clawdex database and Antiy CERT’s 12 documented attacker accounts as ground truth for computing recall and precision, respectively. This ground truth remains incomplete: neither

analysis claimed exhaustiveness. Oathe Engineering [29] found 88 instruction-layer threats with minimal overlap, and Snyk [30] reported that 36% of all ClawHub skills contain security flaws of some kind. We address this incompleteness in the evaluation.

Matching procedure. We matched skill slugs from the Clawdex IOC list against directory names in the ClawHub archive, then checked matched slugs for membership in similarity clusters.

Precision and recall computation. A true positive is a cluster containing at least one file attributed to a documented attacker account (Antiy CERT’s 12 authors, Koi IOC slugs, or files confirmed through payload inspection). A false positive is a cluster containing no files confirmed malicious by available evidence. A false negative is a Koi IOC-listed skill absent from all clusters. Recall is the fraction of Koi IOC skills present in the archive that appear in at least one cluster. We report precision at both cluster level (fraction of clusters containing confirmed malicious content) and file level (fraction of clustered files confirmed malicious).

This framework contains a circularity limitation: the known malware author list was constructed partly through inspection of the same clusters being evaluated. Precision values are lower bounds. Some clusters classified as false positives may contain undiscovered malicious content.

3.5 Behavioral Pattern Scanning

We separately performed grep-based behavioral scanning of the full 23,806-skill ClawHub archive for known malicious patterns (Appendix B); results did not influence cluster interpretation. Scanned patterns included base64 decode operations, curl-pipe-to-shell, environment variable exfiltration, prompt injection, remote instruction fetch, and reverse shell indicators. These counts include legitimate security tools; raw figures are upper bounds on suspicious content.

3.6 Tool: Plugin Librarian

Plugin Librarian¹ is an open-source Python tool implementing the methodology described above. It uses `datasketch` for MinHash/LSH computation, `pyyaml` for SKILL.md frontmatter parsing, and `rich` for terminal output. The CLI handles directory scanning with configurable thresholds (`-threshold`), restricts searches to SKILL.md files (`-skill-only`), excludes designated marketplaces (`-exclude`), and computes marketplace-level similarity matrices.

Output is a JSON report containing file indices, cluster membership, pairwise similarity scores, and marketplace-level overlap metrics. The tool, configuration, and output format are documented in Appendix D.

4 Results

4.1 Ecosystem Characterization (RQ1)

At a 90% Jaccard similarity threshold, 7,147 of 31,634 SKILL.md files (22.6%) appeared in 2,622 clusters. Table 2 and Figure 1 illustrate the sensitivity of this figure to threshold and file selection.

Table 2: Threshold sensitivity on 31,634 SKILL.md files. Recall (hightower6eu subset: 351 of 354 IOC slugs present in the corpus) is 99.2% at all thresholds; full-list recall is 98.8% (337/341, Table 4). The 90% threshold was selected post-hoc from the sweep as the lowest achieving 100% P@ ≥ 20 .

Threshold	Clusters	Clustered	%	P@ ≥ 20	P@ ≥ 10
70%	3,267	9,922	31.4%	69.2%	33.7%
75%	3,129	8,874	28.1%	89.5%	48.3%
80%	2,972	8,199	25.9%	88.2%	69.0%
85%	2,839	7,739	24.5%	88.2%	68.3%
90%	2,622	7,147	22.6%	100.0%	78.9%
95%	2,409	6,547	20.7%	100.0%	81.2%

Sources driving the 22.6% cluster membership fall into two broad categories: non-malicious duplication and attacker campaigns.

Non-malicious duplication. Official skills from the OpenClaw project appear in multiple marketplace repositories because aggregator repos re-publish them. The most-duplicated legitimate skills include frontend-design (10 copies

¹<https://github.com/galeep/plugin-librarian>

Figure 1: $P@ \geq 20$ and $P@ \geq 10$ versus Jaccard threshold. Recall (hightower6eu subset: 351/354) is invariant at 99.2%; precision generally increases with threshold. $P@ \geq 5$ is omitted; see Table 4 for the full breakdown at 90%.

Figure 2: Cluster size distribution at 90% Jaccard threshold. (a) Size histogram; clusters of 20+ files represent 0.4% of all clusters. (b) Type breakdown by size.

across 5 marketplaces), skill-creator (10 copies), writing-skills (8 copies), and humanizer (8 copies). Several marketplace operators also republished skills from other repositories without modification or attribution. The marketplace-level similarity matrix (Section 4.2) quantifies this overlap.

Attack campaigns. Near-identical clusters at 99–100% similarity, generated by single authors at high volume, correspond to supply chain campaigns. We detail these in Section 4.3.

4.2 Marketplace Similarity Matrix

Plugin Librarian computes a marketplace-level similarity score using Jaccard similarity on cluster membership sets. For marketplaces A and B , the similarity is $|C_A \cap C_B|/|C_A \cup C_B|$, where C_X is the set of cluster IDs containing files from marketplace X .

The highest pairwise similarity emerged between `every-marketplace` and `side-quest-marketplace` at 53.8%, indicating that they shared over half of their clustered content. Full matrix results appear in the supplementary material.

4.3 Method Behavior on Malicious Content (RQ2)

We examined the largest clusters at $\geq 99\%$ mean pairwise similarity for common authorship and content patterns. This process identified four distinct campaigns, summarized in Table 3. Antiy CERT [11] reports higher file counts for Campaigns 1–2 across historical data (677 and 390 respectively), likely reflecting skills published after or removed before our snapshot. Campaigns 3–4 include actors documented by Antiy CERT (`zaycv`, `jordanprater`) alongside actors absent from published IOC lists (`thiagoruss0`). Appendix A provides full campaign details.

Table 3: Campaigns detected through similarity clustering (March 13, 2026 archive snapshot).

Campaign	Author(s)	Files	Sim.	Property demonstrated
1	<code>hightower6eu</code>	340	99.8%	Category recovery
2	<code>sakaen736jih</code>	204	~99%	Scale detection
3	<code>thiagoruss0</code>	38	~95%	Source-copy clustering
4	<code>zaycv</code> , <code>jordanprater</code>	28	~97%	Infrastructure linking
Minor	various	19	varies	Shared infrastructure

The clustering behavior highlights several detection properties of the method.

Unsupervised structure recovery. The 340 files in Campaign 1 targeted ten distinct product categories, including cryptocurrency wallets, trading platforms, and productivity tools. The scanner grouped these files into subclusters corresponding to the category structure without receiving any category labels. Template reuse within each category was high enough to produce subclusters, while cross-category template similarity was high enough to link them into a single campaign. MinHash clustering thus recovers campaign structure from content alone.

Detection through source-copy relationships. Campaign 3 copied legitimate skills from established publishers, appending random suffixes to the skill names (e.g., `web-searchuigr`, `transcribeexx`), and injected a small payload block (four lines of prerequisite download instructions). Because the injected content was a small fraction of each document, the modified files clustered with their unmodified source material. The author appeared across 14 distinct clusters, each pairing one of their skills with its legitimate source. An author appearing in many clusters without being the original publisher is itself a triage signal; behavioral scanning lacks this property.

Infrastructure linking. Campaign 4 used four distinct payload variants across its 28 files. A behavioral scanner treating each payload URL independently would see four unrelated indicators; the structural scanner linked them through content similarity, exposing the single-author pattern. Minor actors shared payload infrastructure with Campaigns 1 and 4, visible through cluster adjacency.

Downstream propagation. One aggregator repository ingested a poisoned skill from Campaign 3, propagating malicious content downstream. The ingested copy clustered with both its legitimate source and its Campaign 3 sibling, mapping the propagation path.

4.4 IOC Validation

Of the 341 skill slugs in Koi Security’s original ClawHavoc IOC list, 337 resided in the ClawHub archive. All 337 appeared in similarity clusters (100% within-archive recall). The remaining four were absent from the archive entirely: three AuthTool-related skills likely removed before the snapshot, and one slug with a probable naming discrepancy. Against Koi’s full 341-slug list, recall is $337/341 = 98.8\%$. Tables 2 and 5 use the narrower `hightower6eu` subset (354 IOC slugs) because those experiments were scoped to a single author. Two of the 354 slugs were absent from the corpus (likely removed before the snapshot); of the 352 present, 351 appeared in clusters (99.7% in-corpus; 99.2% against the full 354). Recall against the larger sets (Koi’s updated 824, Antiy’s 1,184) remains unknown because many skills were removed from ClawHub before our snapshot.

Table 4: Precision and recall at cluster size thresholds (≥ 5 files). Precision is cluster-level: a cluster is a true positive if it contains ≥ 1 known-malicious file. Recall is file-level against Koi’s 341-slug IOC list (337 present in archive).

Threshold	Precision	Wilson 95% CI	Clusters	Recall
≥ 20 files	100.0%	[74.1, 100]	11/11	98.8%
≥ 15 files	100.0%	[85.7, 100]	23/23	98.8%
≥ 10 files	78.9%	[63.7, 88.9]	30/38	98.8%
≥ 5 files	36.8%	[29.8, 44.4]	60/163	98.8%
Scaffold [†]	100.0%	[92.0, 100]	44/44	98.8%
All clusters	4.0%	[3.3, 4.8]	104/2,622	98.8%

[†]Scaffold: ≥ 5 files from one source at $\geq 98\%$ similarity (definitional; see Section 5.2).

Table 4 reports precision and recall at different cluster size thresholds. The scanner does not classify clusters as malicious; an analyst triages them using structural properties (size, similarity, authorship) as signals. Cluster size proves an effective prioritization heuristic: at the ≥ 10 threshold, 78.9% of examined clusters contain confirmed malicious content ($n = 38$; Wilson 95% CI [63.7, 88.9]). Restricting to clusters of 20 or more files raises precision to 100% ($n = 11$; 95% CI [74.1, 100]) while capturing all IOC-listed campaigns. Figure 2 confirms that these large clusters constitute a small fraction of the total. Below ≥ 10 , precision degrades as legitimate duplication (aggregator repos, popular skill copies) dominates.

The ground truth is incomplete. The combined IOC corpus from Koi Security, Antiy CERT, Oathe Engineering, and Snyk covers overlapping but non-exhaustive subsets of ClawHub’s malicious content, so true precision may exceed reported figures (Section 3.4).

Validation against known actors. Of the 12 attacker accounts documented by Antiy CERT, our analysis recovered 9: eight through cluster membership and one (as1aep123) through payload URL inspection within clustered files using the `cluster-query grep` tool. Two accounts were absent from the archive, and one (moonshine-100rze) had too few surviving files to cluster. Six additional accounts of interest were identified; five appeared in clusters and one did not. Two of the five are documented by Trend Micro [12]. Appendix A provides the full cross-reference.

4.5 Structural vs. Behavioral Detection (RQ3)

Structural and behavioral detection operate on different signals and exhibit complementary coverage profiles.

Structural detection (this work) identifies campaigns through content similarity. It requires no prior knowledge of payloads, domains, or attack techniques. The reuse pattern serves as the signal, not the payload content. It is effective when an attacker publishes many similar files (a campaign), and ineffective when an attacker publishes a single unique file with novel malicious content.

Behavioral detection (Koi ClawHavoc, Antiy CERT) identifies individual malicious files through content-aware analysis: recognizing suspicious download instructions, known payload infrastructure, and obfuscated commands within skill text. It catches files regardless of whether they belong to a broader campaign. It requires domain knowledge of attack patterns and remains vulnerable to novel payload techniques or obfuscation.

The source-copy campaign (Campaign 3 in Table 3) illustrates this complementarity. The injected payload was a four-line block within an otherwise legitimate skill. A behavioral scanner would flag the download URL if it matched a known pattern. The structural scanner caught these files because they clustered with their unmodified source material. Neither method alone would reliably catch a single well-crafted malicious skill containing unique content and using an unknown payload domain.

Overlap quantification. To measure this complementarity, we ran simplified `grep`-based behavioral pattern matching (base64 decode, `curl-pipe-shell`, environment variable exfiltration, prompt injection, remote instruction fetch, reverse shell indicators) across the 23,806 ClawHub SKILL.md files. Of the 1,784 files matching at least one behavioral pattern, only 321 (18.0%) also appeared in similarity clusters. This low overlap suggests limited redundancy between the two approaches, though the comparison is approximate: our `grep` patterns are a simplified proxy for the behavioral analysis performed by Koi Security and Antiy CERT, and the 1,784 matches include false positives from legitimate security-related content. The figure is an upper bound on structural-only detections, not a precise measure of complementarity.

Temporal features. The malicious campaigns exhibited anomalous publishing patterns, with hundreds of skills from single authors in compressed timeframes, suggesting rate anomaly detection as a complementary signal. We did not implement or evaluate this.

5 Discussion

5.1 Method Transfer and Dual-Purpose Value

The primary finding is that the same operational pattern exploited by ACME and MPHunter in code registries, campaign-scale template reuse, is present in this text-based ecosystem and equally detectable by similarity clustering. Whether the template is a JavaScript postinstall script, a Python `setup.py`, or a markdown `SKILL.md` file, the operational pattern of producing many near-identical artifacts creates a detectable structural fingerprint. This transfer is not guaranteed. AST-based and document-level clustering operate on different feature spaces; what transfers is the detection principle that campaigns leave a structural trace, and similarity methods find it regardless of artifact type.

This claim operates within boundaries: one registry, one attack type (mass template flooding), one similarity method. The Agent Skills standard’s adoption across 30+ platforms means validated patterns are directly relevant to other registries implementing the same specification. Whether transfer holds for structurally different ecosystems (prompt registries, MCP server directories) or other attack types remains open. Two alternative methods on the same corpus (Section 5.2) achieved comparable recall but lower precision, confirming the principle is not method-specific.

The dual-purpose nature of similarity analysis deserves emphasis. We built the scanner to flag duplicate skills that consume agent context window budget. It surfaced malware campaigns instead. This overlap has a structural explanation, though the parallel is not exact: mass plagiarism and mass supply chain attacks share an operational property, namely one actor producing many near-identical files [28, 24]. A tool designed to catch the first will catch the second when both are present. This does not mean all quality metrics are security metrics, but similarity monitoring provides dual-purpose value when campaigns rely on template reuse. The reverse also holds: a security-motivated similarity scan will surface quality problems like plagiarism and content duplication, lowering the cost-benefit barrier for deploying either type of monitoring.

5.2 Comparison with Trivial Baselines

Two trivial detection methods establish context for the MinHash clustering results.

Author submission count. Flagging all ClowHub authors who published N or more skills produces high recall for the known campaign accounts but poor precision. At $N \geq 5$, all 564 skills by the two primary campaign authors are captured, but only 7 of 745 flagged authors are known malicious (0.9% precision). At $N \geq 20$, precision rises to 5.3% but author-level recall drops to 33.3% (5 of 15 IOC-listed authors with ≥ 1 skill in the archive). The core problem is that many legitimate authors publish prolifically: 28 of the top 30 ClowHub authors by volume are non-malicious.

Exact file hash deduplication. SHA-256 hashing all 31,634 `SKILL.md` files produces 1,946 duplicate groups. Of these, 71 (3.6%) contain known malicious authors. Hash-based recall for the two primary campaign authors’ skills is 95.4% (538 of 564 files share at least one exact duplicate), compared to MinHash clustering’s 98.8%. The 26 files missed by exact hashing (4.6% of the 564) contain per-skill template variations (different names or descriptions in YAML frontmatter) that change enough bytes to produce different hashes while preserving the malicious payload structure.

The precision gap is the more significant finding. An analyst triaging exact-hash duplicate groups faces a 96.4% false positive rate across 1,946 groups. MinHash clustering at the ≥ 20 threshold produces 11 clusters, all confirmed malicious (100% cluster-level precision). Structural similarity reduces the triage set by two orders of magnitude while capturing near-duplicate variants that exact matching misses.

The scaffold definition (5+ files from a single source at 98%+ similarity) was established during the January 2026 quality analysis, before the ClowHavoc report, to characterize mass duplication patterns. It captures mass flooding by construction, so its 100% precision is a consequence of the definition. The baselines above clarify MinHash’s added value: grouping near-duplicates that exact hashing misses, and distinguishing campaigns from legitimate duplication.

TF-IDF cosine similarity. As a standard information retrieval baseline, we computed TF-IDF vectors (50,000 features, 1–3-grams, sublinear TF) and clustered files exceeding 0.9 cosine similarity using the same greedy first-match algorithm. TF-IDF produced 3,170 clusters covering 9,208 files (29.1%), with comparable recall (99.7%) but substantially lower precision: $P@ \geq 20$ dropped to 75.0% (15/20) and $P@ \geq 10$ to 41.1% (30/73), compared to MinHash’s 100% ($P@ \geq 20$) and 78.9% ($P@ \geq 10$). Runtime was 465 s versus 305 s for MinHash (both wall time). The precision

Figure 3: Similarity method comparison on 31,634 SKILL.md files. (a) Cluster-level precision; all methods achieve $\geq 99.7\%$ recall (not shown). (b) Wall-clock runtime (8-core i9-9880H).

Table 5: Shingle size ablation at 90% Jaccard threshold. Recall denominator is 352 corpus files (vs. 354 IOC slugs in Table 2). 3-grams maximize $P@ \geq 20$.

Shingle	Clusters	Clustered	Recall	$P@ \geq 20$	$P@ \geq 10$
2-gram	2,693	7,344 (23.2%)	99.7% (351/352)	100% (14/14)	75.7% (28/37)
3-gram*	2,622	7,147 (22.6%)	99.7% (351/352)	100% (11/11)	78.9% (30/38)
4-gram	2,539	6,939 (21.9%)	99.7% (351/352)	93.3% (14/15)	81.8% (27/33)

*This work.

gap reflects TF-IDF’s sensitivity to shared vocabulary: files discussing similar topics cluster together even when they are independently authored.

Sentence embeddings. We encoded all files using all-MiniLM-L6-v2 [33] (384-dimensional embeddings, first 2,048 characters per file) and clustered at 0.9 cosine similarity. Embeddings produced 3,626 clusters covering 9,462 files (29.9%) with 99.7% recall. Precision fell between TF-IDF and MinHash: $P@ \geq 20$ was 92.9% (13/14) and $P@ \geq 10$ was 62.8% (27/43). Runtime was 924 s (805 s encoding, 119 s clustering), three times slower than MinHash. Semantic embeddings outperform TF-IDF by capturing meaning-level similarity, but MinHash’s word-level shingling more faithfully captures the sequential structure of copy-paste attacks. All three methods were compared at 0.9, but Jaccard and cosine similarity are different metrics, so the operating points are not strictly equivalent. At this threshold, MinHash achieves the highest precision and lowest runtime, though the precision differences are not statistically significant (Fisher’s exact test as approximate indicator, since methods share the same corpus: MinHash vs. TF-IDF $p = 0.13$; MinHash vs. embeddings $p = 1.0$, which reflects insufficient power to detect differences at these sample sizes). All three methods detect these campaigns; MinHash’s primary advantage is speed and simplicity. Figure 3 summarizes the precision and runtime comparison across all three methods. Recall ($\geq 99.2\%$) is omitted from the figure because all methods achieve near-identical values.

Shingle size ablation. We repeated the MinHash analysis with 2-gram and 4-gram word shingles (Table 5). All three sizes found the same 351 hightower6eu files in clusters (99.7% of 352 in the corpus). Precision varies: 2-grams produce more topical false positives ($P@ \geq 10$: 75.7% vs. 78.9%), while 4-grams fragment one campaign, dropping $P@ \geq 20$ to 93.3%. The 3-gram default maximizes precision. Runtime is comparable across sizes (≈ 250 s, excluding I/O overhead).

5.3 Implications and Blind Spots

Registry operators should run MinHash similarity against new submissions at publish time. This would flag mass-produced content before it reaches consumers, and MinHash paired with LSH scales sublinearly in corpus size for candidate retrieval. Rate limiting or anomaly alerting on per-author submission velocity would complement similarity monitoring, given the campaigns’ concentrated publishing patterns. The aggregation model propagated malicious content downstream, so tracking provenance across aggregators would enable targeted removal when upstream content is flagged.

Structural similarity detection also has inherent blind spots that parameter tuning cannot address. A skill containing novel malicious content that avoids resembling any other file in the corpus will not cluster, because clustering requires volume. The Koi report documented a skill called `better-polymarket` that contained functional, legitimate code hiding a covert backdoor; if such a file is sufficiently distinct from standard templates or lacks template siblings in the corpus, structural similarity will not flag it. An attacker who produces many malicious skills while varying the content between them (different wording, different structure, only the payload in common) will evade detection at high similarity thresholds, because the shared payload alone rarely generates enough n-gram overlap to exceed the 90% threshold. LAMPS [6] demonstrated this limitation empirically: MPHunter’s clustering missed obfuscated packages that varied their surface structure. These blind spots define the boundary of the method’s applicability and motivate pairing it with behavioral scanning.

6 Limitations

MinHash estimation error. With 128 permutations, the Jaccard similarity estimate has a standard error of 8.8% (95% CI half-width: 17.3%). Files near the threshold boundary may be inconsistently clustered across runs.

Natural language vs. code. MinHash on word-level shingles is less precise than AST-based methods for code. Topical similarity in natural language (two skills about the same subject) can produce moderate Jaccard scores without indicating copying or attack activity. The 90% threshold suppresses but does not eliminate this noise.

Incomplete ground truth and small precision samples. No single IOC list covers the full ecosystem; some clusters classified as benign may contain malicious content not yet documented. At the ≥ 10 cluster-size threshold, all 30 true positives contain files from authors independently documented by Koi Security, Antiy CERT, or Trend Micro [12]: the clusters trace to Campaigns 1–2 (`hightower6eu`, `sakaen736jih`; documented by both Koi and Antiy), Campaign 4 (`zaycv`, `jordanprater`; Antiy), and minor actors listed in Table 6. None depend on our own cluster-derived labels. The circularity caveat (Section 3.4) therefore does not affect the reported 78.9% precision at this threshold. It does affect precision at smaller thresholds (≥ 5), where clusters containing only self-identified authors contribute to the true positive count. The headline result (100% at ≥ 20 files) rests on only 11 clusters (Wilson 95% CI [74.1, 100]); a single false positive would reduce it to 91%. The 100-character content filter excluded 152 stub files; four belonged to a known malicious author but contained only empty YAML frontmatter with no instructions or payload.

Several methodological caveats constrain interpretation. Greedy cluster membership depends on processing order (Section 3.3); the seed robustness experiment measures hash randomness ($\text{ARI} \geq 0.9999$) but does not isolate index ordering, and the shingle ablation (Table 5) covers word-level 2–4-grams but not character-level shingling. All results are retrospective: a prospective deployment would produce identical clusters for any file present at scan time, but whether future campaigns will use the same template-reuse patterns is untested. The corpus reflects a single snapshot in which four IOC-listed skills were absent (likely removed before collection) and approximately 34 macOS case-insensitive filesystem collisions caused minor undercounting.

Author submission count alone achieves 100% recall at $N \geq 5$ but only 0.9% precision (Section 5.2); MinHash clustering reduces the triage set from 745 flagged authors to 11 clusters, all confirmed malicious. An attacker aware of similarity monitoring could vary templates enough to drop below the Jaccard threshold, but the campaigns here made no such effort, consistent with an ecosystem lacking structural defenses at the time of attack. Results are from one ecosystem (ClawHub / OpenClaw), and generalization to other text-based registries is untested.

This analysis used publicly available data from public GitHub repositories. Active payload infrastructure was reported to ClawHub maintainers, and we report only attacker accounts already published by prior security analyses.

7 Related Work

Clustering-based malware detection. Section 2.3 introduced the clustering lineage (ACME [2], MPHunter [3], EMPHunter [4]). The closest methodological parallel is Sejfić and Schäfer [25], who combined ML classifiers with textual

clone detection to identify near-copies of known malicious npm packages. Our work differs in artifact type (natural-language documents rather than code) and in using unsupervised MinHash clustering without a trained classifier.

Text-based similarity for spam and phishing. Template clustering has prior application to text-based security threats: Xie et al. [34] clustered spam emails by URL template to identify botnet campaigns, Gao et al. [35] detected coordinated social network spam via near-duplicate clustering, and Merlo et al. [36] found that 90% of phishing kits share 90%+ source code with at least one other kit. Our work applies the same principle to a package ecosystem, where artifacts reside in a registry and detection occurs at publish time.

Behavioral and hybrid detection. Garrett et al. [27] introduced unsupervised anomaly detection for npm package updates. Cerebro [5] models behavioral sequences in npm and PyPI packages. LAMPS [6] applies multi-agent LLM-based analysis. PyPIMalDet [7] combines code and metadata features. These approaches complement structural clustering and target different attack patterns.

Ecosystem security and dynamic detection. Zimmermann et al. [24] demonstrated that individual npm packages can impact large parts of the ecosystem through dependency chains. Vu et al. [37] analyzed PyPI package lifecycle metadata to detect malicious updates. Zahan et al. [38] studied npm supply chain weak links including maintainer account hygiene and install scripts. Datadog’s GuardDog [10] detected cross-ecosystem campaigns using behavioral analysis. OSCAR [22] bridges academic detection and production deployment. Socket, Snyk, and Phylum provide production supply chain scanning for code ecosystems; none targets text-based skill registries.

Supply chain attack taxonomy and typosquatting. Ladisa et al. [9] catalog 107 attack vectors across 94 incidents; the campaigns here fall under typosquatting, combosquatting, and registry flooding. Vu et al. [19] and Duan et al. [23] characterized squatting attacks across npm, PyPI, and RubyGems. Taylor et al. [20] proposed SpellBound for install-time typosquatting detection.

AI skill ecosystem security. Six separate analyses have documented security threats in the ClawHub ecosystem (Section 1). Koi Security [8] and Antiy CERT [11] analyzed the ClawHavoc campaign through behavioral pattern matching and binary reverse engineering respectively. Trend Micro [12] provided binary analysis of the AMOS stealer payloads and published additional attacker IOCs. Oathe Engineering [29] found 88 instruction-layer threats. Snyk [30] reported 36% of skills contain security flaws. Bitdefender [31] analyzed the stealer payloads. All six operate at the payload, behavioral, or instruction level; none applies structural document similarity.

Adversarial tool injection. Zhang et al. [32] demonstrated adversarial tool injection against LLM-integrated applications (91%+ success), establishing the threat model our structural detection addresses.

8 Conclusion

Document similarity clustering detects coordinated template-reuse supply chain campaigns in AI agent skill marketplaces. Applied to 31,634 files in 305 seconds wall time (280 s user CPU) on a single workstation (Intel i9-9880H, 64 GB RAM), MinHash with 3-word shingles achieved 100% within-archive recall (337/337; 4 IOC entries absent from corpus; high recall is expected by construction for template-reuse campaigns) and cluster-level precision of 78.9% across 38 clusters of ≥ 10 files (Wilson 95% CI [63.7, 88.9]), rising to 100% for the 11 largest (≥ 20 files; 95% CI [74.1, 100], where a single false positive would reduce precision to 91%). Validated against published attacker account lists from six independent security analyses, the method recovered 9 of 12 documented accounts (8 via clustering, 1 via payload inspection within clustered files). These results demonstrate that the clustering-based detection approach, established by ACME and MPHunter on code ecosystems, transfers to a text-based artifact type for template-reuse campaigns.

The method cannot detect single unique malicious files, sophisticated backdoors, or campaigns with high content variation (Section 5.3). Reported precision values are lower bounds, as the known-malicious author list was constructed partly from the clusters being evaluated (Section 3.4).

The AI skill marketplace has measurable quality and security problems: 22.6% of files fall into similarity clusters and multiple active malware campaigns were present in the corpus. Git commit history suggests that the largest campaign had already formed a multi-file similarity cluster in the archive by the time of public disclosure, under conservative assumptions about disclosure timing. The low computational cost makes similarity monitoring practical for ingest pipelines.

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A IOC Cross-Reference

Table 6 cross-references attacker accounts from published analyses against our structural clustering results. Of 12 Antiy CERT-documented accounts, 8 appeared in similarity clusters and a 9th (`aslaep123`) was found through payload URL inspection within clustered files. Two accounts (`gpaitai`, `danman60`) had no files in the archive at the time of our snapshot. One account (`moonshine-100rze`) had 3 surviving files that did not cluster. Six additional accounts of interest were identified. Five appeared in clusters; the sixth (`anisafifi`, 4 skills) did not cluster. Two of the five (`thiagoruss0`, `stveenli`) are documented by Trend Micro [12]. We make no novelty claim for the remaining accounts, as private threat databases may already cover them.

Table 6: Attacker accounts: prior documentation vs. structural clustering. Skills column shows the count reported by the citing source (not corpus count; see Table 3 for corpus figures). Antiy = Antiy CERT, Koi = Koi Security, TM = Trend Micro.

Account	Skills	Documented by	Clustered?
<code>hightower6eu</code>	677	Antiy, Koi	Scaffold
<code>sakaen736jih</code>	390	Antiy, Koi	Scaffold
<code>moonshine-100rze</code>	60	Antiy	3 files, unclustered
<code>zaycv</code>	19	Antiy	Scaffold
<code>aslaep123</code>	14	Antiy	Via payload grep
<code>jordanprater</code>	10	Antiy	Scaffold
<code>noreplyboter</code>	4	Antiy	Internal (2 files)
<code>rjnpag</code>	2	Antiy	Internal (2 files)
<code>lvy19811120-gif</code>	2	Antiy	Internal (3 files)
<code>gpaitai</code>	2	Antiy	Not in archive
<code>danman60</code>	2	Antiy	Not in archive
<code>noyppearl</code>	2	Antiy	Cross-mkt (5 files)
<code>thiagoruss0</code>	28	TM	Cross-mkt (14 cl.)
<code>stveenli</code>	8	TM	Internal (2 files)
<code>anisafifi</code>	4	—	Unclassified
<code>timclawbot</code>	4	—	Cross-mkt (5 files)
<code>kenblive</code>	3	—	Internal (5 files)
<code>mupengi-bot</code>	2	—	Cross-mkt (6 cl.)

B Behavioral Pattern Scan

This appendix reports the behavioral pattern scan described in Section 3.5.

Table 7: Behavioral pattern scan results (raw counts). Counts include legitimate content sharing attack-pattern vocabulary and represent upper bounds.

Pattern	Count
Base64 decode operations	175
curl-pipe-to-shell	443
Env secrets + HTTP calls	810
Prompt injection language	102
Remote instruction fetch (C2)	242
Reverse shell indicators	20

We did not manually classify individual matches. Without per-match classification, these counts carry limited interpretive value. Their purpose is to indicate the scale of the ecosystem’s attack surface, not to identify specific malicious files. They were not used to inform cluster interpretation or the precision/recall analysis reported in Section 4.4.

Additional behavioral indicators observed in the archive include hardcoded credentials (API keys, GitHub personal access tokens, AWS credentials) published in skill files, `SOUL.md` and `MEMORY.md` modification patterns (a persistence vector specific to the OpenClaw agent framework), and hot-reload or remote instruction fetch patterns that could serve as command-and-control channels in an AI agent context.

C Suspicious Scaffold Clusters

Several scaffold-type clusters (single marketplace, ≥ 5 files, $\geq 98\%$ similarity) exhibited patterns consistent with campaign activity but lacked sufficient evidence for confirmed classification at the time of analysis.

orlyjamie published skills named `testing-maliicious-vt` (8 copies) and `peacefulskill` (7 copies). The misspelling “maliicious” and the volume of near-identical copies are consistent with testing or staging activity for a campaign. `krajekisbtc` published 8 `polymarketbtc` copies, matching the Polymarket-themed targeting pattern observed in Campaigns 1 and 4.

A cluster spanning five accounts (`aisadocs`, `Oxjordansg-yolo`, `aisapay`, `chaimengphp`, `bowen-dotcom`) contained near-identical skills across nominally independent accounts, suggesting a single operator or coordinated group.

These clusters could expand the known malicious actor list but require further investigation before attribution. We document them here for completeness and to support future analysis.

D Reproduction

Plugin Librarian is open source (Python 3.10+, `datasketch`) and available at <https://github.com/galeep/plugin-librarian>. The ClawHub archive was cloned on 2026-03-13 at commit `16c991de`. Community marketplace repositories (31 repos, plus 26 curated sub-repositories) were cloned between 2026-01-02 and 2026-03-13. Per-repository commit SHAs are recorded in the supplementary materials. To reproduce the primary analysis:

Listing 1: Reproduction steps.

```
1 git clone https://github.com/openclaw/skills
2 librarian scan --dir ./skills \
3   --threshold 0.9 --skill-only
4 librarian stats
```